

DETERMINATION OF ONTOGENETIC VARIABILITY IN TUBEROSE [*AGAVE AMICA (MEDIK.) THIEDE & GOVAERTS*] PLANT

Esra YILMAZ

Department of Field Crops, Faculty of Agriculture, Harran University
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7936-7380>

Özet

Bu çalışma, sümbülteberde (*Agave amica* (Medik.) Thiede & Govaerts) ontogenetik değişkenliğin (farklı çiçek hasat zamanlarının) uçucu yağ oranı, verim ve bazı agronomik özellikler üzerindeki etkilerini belirlemek amacıyla yürütülmüştür. Deneme, 2024 yılı yaz yetiştirme sezonunda Şanlıurfa koşullarında gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırma, dört farklı çiçek hasat zamanı (tomurcuk dönemi, çiçeğin tam açıldığı gün, çiçek açımından 1 gün sonra ve çiçek açımından 2 gün sonra) kullanılarak üç tekerrürlü tesadüf blokları deneme desenine göre kurulmuştur. Çıkış süresi, ilk çiçeklenme zamanı (gün), %70 çiçeklenme zamanı (gün), son çiçeklenme zamanı (gün), başakta çiçeklenme süresi (gün) ve vejetasyon süresi (gün) gibi fenolojik gözlemler kaydedilmiştir. Ayrıca bitki boyu (45,66–46,70 cm), başak başına çiçek sayısı (29,33–30,00 çiçek başak⁻¹), başak uzunluğu (82,66–87,70 cm) ve uçucu yağ oranı (%0,17–0,38) belirlenmiştir. Araştırma sonuçlarına göre en yüksek uçucu yağ oranı, çiçeklerin tam açıldığı gün hasat edilen örneklerden elde edilmiştir. Bulgular, sümbülteberde uçucu yağ oranının ontogenetik gelişim dönemine bağlı olarak değiştiğini ve en yüksek değerine tam çiçeklenme döneminde ulaştığını göstermiştir. Bu nedenle, uçucu yağ üretimi amacıyla çiçeklerin tam çiçeklenme döneminde hasat edilmesi önerilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sümbülteber, Çiçek, Verim, Ontogenetik Değişkenlik, Agave

Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the effects of ontogenetic variability (different flower-harvest times) on essential oil content, yield, and certain agronomic characteristics of tuberose (*Agave amica* (Medik.) Thiede & Govaerts). The experiment was carried out under Şanlıurfa conditions during the 2024 summer growing season. The research was established according to a randomized complete block design with three replications using four different flower harvest times (bud stage, the day of full flower opening, 1 day after flower opening, and 2 days after flower opening). Phenological observations, including emergence date, first flowering date (days), 70% flowering date (days), last flowering date (days), flowering period of the spike (days), and vegetation period (days), were recorded. In addition, plant height (45.66–46.70 cm), number of flowers per spike (29.33–30.00 flowers spike⁻¹), spike length (82.66–87.70 cm), and essential oil content (0.17–0.38%) were determined. According to the results of the study, the highest essential oil content was obtained from flowers harvested on the day of full flower opening. The findings revealed that the essential oil content of tuberose varied depending on the ontogenetic developmental stage and reached its maximum value at the full flowering stage. Therefore, harvesting flowers at the fully flowering stage is recommended for essential oil production.

Keywords: Tuberose, Flower, Yield, Ontogenetic Variability, Agave

1. INTRODUCTION

Medicinal and aromatic plants have been used to treat various diseases in traditional, alternative, and modern medicine throughout history. Furthermore, these plants play a significant role in the pharmaceutical industry for drug production, in the preparation of dietary supplements, in the cosmetics and perfumery sectors, and in the food industry as spices due to their aromatic and flavor-enhancing properties (Acıbuca and Budak, 2018).

Among medicinal and aromatic plants, the tuberose [*Agave amica* (Medik.) Thiede & Govaerts] is a tuberous, perennial plant belonging to the Asparagaceae family; there are 273 *Agave* species distributed worldwide (Anonymous, 2024). Due to its fragrant flowers, long vase life, and high economic value, it is valued as an ornamental plant, cut flower, and source of essential oil (Taş, 2022). The essential oil extracted from its flowers is in high demand, particularly in the perfumery and cosmetics industries; it also holds pharmaceutical significance due to its antibacterial, antifungal, and insecticidal properties (Naga et al., 2020). In recent years, increasing global demand has boosted interest in agave cultivation and essential oil production.

The quantity and quality of essential oil in the tuberose are the primary factors that directly influence the economic value of the final product. However, these characteristics can vary depending on the plant's genetic makeup, growing conditions, and developmental stage. In particular, ontogenetic variability refers to changes in the quantity and composition of active compounds during different growth stages of the plant, and it is of great importance for the production of high-quality raw material and the determination of the optimal harvest time (Mokhtarzadeh et al., 2023).

This study was conducted to determine the ontogenetic variability of the tuberose plant grown under the ecological conditions of Şanlıurfa. The plant's adaptation capacity, yield performance, and certain agronomic features were analysed in the study; it attempted to find the ideal harvest time by studying changes in active chemicals during different growth phases. The results are intended to provide scientific contributions to the development of tuberose cultivation under Şanlıurfa conditions, the production of high-quality essential oil, and future research in this field.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used corms of the *Agave amica* 'Single' variety, with a circumference of 8–10 cm. The experiment was conducted in the 2024 summer growing season using a randomized block design with three replicates. The experimental field was plowed with a plow before planting, followed by weed removal; fertilizer was then applied, and the field preparation was completed by tilling with a disc harrow. Before planting, a basal fertilizer of 13.18.15+(2MgO) +(10SO₃) was applied at a rate of 40 kg/ha. Before flowering, 10.30.10+Trace elements fertilizer was applied at a rate of 5 kg/ha to strengthen roots, promote flowering, and enhance maturation. Seed tubers were stored in a warehouse maintained at 16°C and 65% humidity. Planting was done by hand at a spacing of 15 cm within rows and 30 cm between rows, at a depth of 10 cm. After planting, the experimental area was irrigated using a sprinkler system, and subsequent irrigation was performed as needed. Weed control was carried out manually after planting. An ultrasonic dog repellent was installed in the experimental area to prevent damage from dogs.

2.1. Examined Attributes

Plant Height (cm): The height of 20 plants randomly selected from each plot was measured from the soil surface to the tip of the leaves in centimeters, and the averages were calculated.

Flower Stem Length (cm): The distance from the soil surface to the tip of the flower stem was measured in centimeters for 20 randomly selected plants in each plot, and the averages were calculated.

Number of Flowers per Stem (flowers/stem): The number of flowers on the flower stem was counted for 20 randomly selected plants in each plot, and the averages were calculated.

Essential oil yield (L/ha): The essential oil yield per hectare was determined in liters by using the amount of essential oil obtained from 1,000 flowers and the flower yield per hectare

2.2. The Enfleurage Method

A study was conducted to determine the optimal harvest time based on ontogenetic variability, which refers to changes in the content of active ingredients at different developmental stages. Four distinct harvest times were tested according to the flowering stage: the bud stage, the day the flower fully opened, one day after flowering, and two days after flowering.

The enfleurage method was utilized to measure the quantity of essential oil. This technique is a cold-oil extraction method specifically designed for certain delicate and sensitive flowers, such as jasmine, hyacinth, and violet, from which oil cannot be extracted directly through distillation. The process was conducted on a glass plate positioned within a rectangular wooden frame (or box) that measures 5 cm in height, 50 cm in length, and 40 cm in width. 400 g of shea butter was spread onto the glass plate, taking care not to let it touch the wooden frame. Flower stems that were about to bloom were harvested with pruning shears, placed in a vase containing water mixed with a flower nutrient solution, and the flowers were picked according to their harvest times. The collected flowers were then weighed on a precision scale and counted. The flowers were placed on the glass plate coated with oil and left to sit for 24 hours. The flowers were replaced every 24 hours, and this process was repeated 10 times. During this process, the shea butter was saturated with flower oil. This saturated oil is referred to as "pomat" (Talati., 2017).

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Phenological Observations

As shown in Table 1, the emergence period of tuberose grown under Şanlıurfa conditions was determined to be 21 days. The value observed in the present study was consistent with the emergence period of 12–14 days reported by Taş (2022), while it was earlier than the emergence period of 39–46.33 days reported by Deka and Talukdar (2017). These differences may be attributed to variations in cultivation practices, climatic conditions, and soil characteristics.

When the first flowering time presented in Table 1 was examined, it was determined that the earliest flowering occurred 46 days after tuber planting. This result indicated earlier flowering compared with the values reported by Safeena et al. (2019), who recorded 105.76–112 days, and Taş (2022), who reported 69 days. This difference may be attributed to the fact that the formation and development of flower primordia in tuberose are closely related to the nutrient reserves contained within the tuber. Larger tubers tend to flower earlier and produce more vigorous shoots due to their greater stored nutrient content.

In the present study, the flowering period of the spike was determined to be 26 days. The value obtained in the present study was higher than the range of 16.50–22.40 days reported by Kumar et al. (2012) and was similar to the value of 30 days reported by Taş (2022). The differences observed in the flowering period of tuberose spikes are mainly because the flowers on a spike do not bloom simultaneously. This is because the florets open sequentially from the lower part of the spike toward the upper part at intervals of several days.

When the last flowering date was examined, it was determined that flowering ended 214 days after the first flowering date. The last flowering date obtained in this study was similar to the value of 230 days reported by Taş (2022).

The vegetation period of tuberose grown under Şanlıurfa conditions was determined to be 263 days. Taş (2022) reported vegetation periods of 234 days for daughter bulbs and 253 days for mother bulbs. The findings of the present study were similar to those reported by Taş (2022).

3.2. PLANT CHARACTERISTICS

Table 2 presents mean values of plant height (cm), number of flowers per spike (flowers/spike), spike length (cm), and essential oil content (%) of tuberose at different harvest times.

3.2.1. Plant Heights

As shown in Table 2, plant height ranged between 45.6 and 46.7 cm. The values obtained in the present study were lower than those reported by Sivakumar et al. (2020), who recorded plant heights of 60.2–63.8 cm, and by Harshavardhan et al. (2023), who reported values ranging from 39.0–79.3 cm. However, the results were comparable to the values of 28.62–45.10 cm reported by Taş (2022). These differences may be attributed to variations in the cultivars used as plant material and differences in bulb size among the studies.

3.2.2. Stem length

As shown in Table 2, stem length ranged between 82.6 and 87.7 cm. The values obtained in the present study were higher than those reported by Safeena et al. (2019), who recorded stem lengths of 57.48–71.01 cm, and lower than those reported by Bharathi et al. (2023), who reported values ranging from 55.11–114.51 cm. However, the results were comparable to the stem lengths of 67.62–87.06 cm reported by Saucedo et al. (2023). Since stem length is a trait that is significantly influenced by environmental factors, the differences observed among studies are considered expected.

3.2.3. Flower numbers per stem

As shown in Table 2, the number of flowers per stem ranged between 29.3 and 30.0 flowers stem⁻¹. The values obtained in the present study were higher than the value of 0–24.24 flowers stem⁻¹ reported by Taş (2022), but lower than those reported by Bharathi et al. (2023) (54.87 flowers stem⁻¹), Harshavardhan et al. (2023) (33.8–42.1 flowers stem⁻¹), and Saucedo et al. (2023) (19.30–39.28 flowers stem⁻¹). These differences may be attributed to the genetic variability of the plant materials used, differences in bulb size, and variations in the climatic conditions under which the plants were grown.

3.2.4 Essential oil ratio (%)

As shown in Table 2, the essential oil content of tuberose (*Agave amica*) varied between 0.17 and 0.38% depending on different harvest times. It was determined that the lowest essential oil content was obtained at the bud stage, while the highest value was recorded on the day of full bloom. These results indicate that the essential oil content of the plant shows significant variation depending on the harvest time. The values obtained in this study were higher than those reported by Rathore and Singh (2013) (0.099–0.128%) and lower than those reported by Sari et al. (2019) (0.602–4.297%). These differences may be attributed to variations in extraction methods, growing conditions, genotypic differences, and developmental stages of the flowers. In particular, the variation in volatile compound production in tuberose throughout the flowering process supports that harvest time is a determining factor in essential oil yield.

In particular, the variation in volatile compound production in tuberose throughout the flowering process supports that harvest time is a determining factor in essential oil yield. In this regard, we believe this study will serve as a foundation for future research.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the changes in the production of volatile compounds throughout the flowering process of tuberose demonstrate that determining the appropriate harvest time is of great importance for maximizing essential oil yield. Based on the findings of this study, the optimum flower harvest time for essential oil production in tuberose was determined to be the day of fully bloom. In addition to contributing to the determination of the optimum harvest time in tuberose, this study provides a scientific basis for future research focusing on essential oil production and quality characteristics.

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TABLES

Table 1: Phenological observation values of tuberose

Examined characteristics	
Planting date	4 Nisan 2024
Emergence date	25 Nisan 2024
First flowering time	20 Mayıs 2024
%70 Flowering date	25 Haziran 2024
Last flowering date	20 Aralık 2024
Spike flowering period (days)	26
Flowering period (days)	214
Vegetation duration (day)	263

Table 2: Mean values of plant height (cm), number of flowers per spike (flowers/spike), spike length (cm), and essential oil content (%) of tuberose at different harvest times

Harvest times	Plant Heights	Flower numbers per stem	Stem length	Essential oil ratio (%)
Bud stage	45.66 b	29.33 b	82.66 c	0.17 c
Date of full bloom	46.33 ab	29.66 ab	84.67 b	0.38 a
One day after bloom	46.7 a	30.00 a	87.7 a	0.34 ab
Two days after bloom	46.7 a	30.00 a	87.7 a	0.27 b